

NUMERICAL AND EXPERIMENTAL INVESTIGATION OF LOAD SHARING IN COMPOSITE BONDED-BOLTED JOINTS

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ABSTRACT

Recent experimental studies have highlighted the potential of combining bonding and bolting as a means of increasing the safety factor of bolted joints in composite structures. These *hybrid* joints can achieve greater static and fatigue strength than the underlying bolted joints, but generally only when the adhesive joint strength exceeds the bolted joint strength. However, when there is *load sharing* between the adhesive and bolts, then even a weak adhesive joint has the potential to substantially increase the bolted joint strength. Unfortunately, load sharing is difficult to achieve since the bonded joint is typically significantly stiffer than the bolted joint. This causes the adhesive to transfer most of the load by itself. It is thus of interest to be able to predict the existence and level of load sharing in a hybrid joint *a priori*. In this paper, an efficient numerical model of a composite single-lap, single-bolt hybrid joint is developed for this purpose, which addresses some important shortcomings of the models currently available in the literature. This model is subsequently validated experimentally. The model has the potential to be used in preliminary design studies and sensitivity analyses.

1 INTRODUCTION

Large structures usually consist of multiple smaller subassemblies. In order to transfer loads between these subassemblies, it is necessary to join them together. Joints generally require the relevant subassemblies to partially overlap, whereupon they are connected using either mechanical fasteners (bolting) or structural adhesive (bonding). Critically, the existence of geometric discontinuities, material discontinuities, load asymmetry and contact in the joint regions leads to a highly complex and generally elevated stress state that can engender premature failure of the overall structure. It is thus imperative to carefully design joints to minimize the developed operating stresses. This is particularly important for bolted joints in composite structures, whose brittle nature means that they do not benefit from the plastic stress relief at bolt holes that is typical in metallic bolted joints [1,2].

Although bonding offers significant benefits in this respect (since it distributes the load transfer and limits the developed stress concentrations) this technique cannot currently be certified by itself in primary aircraft structures. This is due to the difficulty of manufacturing and inspecting high-quality bonded joints [3]. The result is an unacceptable variability in their strength. Bolted joints are thus the norm in large aircraft structures, although their theoretical strengths are often lower than those of equivalent bonded joints. Furthermore, their use incurs a significant mass penalty.

In response to the relative inefficiency (low strength-to-mass ratio) of traditional bolted joints, researchers have begun to study the potential benefits of combining bonding and bolting. The resulting *hybrid* joints are, in specific circumstances, stronger than the underlying bolted joints by themselves. This could theoretically allow some bolts to be removed and thereby lead to a lighter overall structure (the impact of the structural adhesive mass is assumed to be small since it would replace the sealant or liquid shims that are already in widespread use in bolted joints). Preliminary inquiries with civil aviation authorities suggest that they would be receptive to a hybrid joint design wherein the underlying bolted joint, by itself, is able to sustain limit load, while the joint as a whole is able to

sustain ultimate load. Although this limits the potential benefits of hybridization, it still provides a window within which efficiencies can be obtained while satisfying certification concerns over joint strength.

Importantly, a number of experimental investigations [4-7] have demonstrated that hybrid joint strength improvements over bolted joints are possible whenever:

- (1) The bonded joint is stronger than the bolted joint
- (2) The bonded joint is weaker than the bolted joint but there is significant *load sharing* between the adhesive and bolts (load sharing means that part of the load is transferred by the bolt and part of it being transferred by the adhesive between subassemblies)

Authors in the literature who did not establish any strength improvement due to hybridization [8] used joints that did not belong in either of these two categories. Among authors who did establish improvements, the biggest reported benefits occurred for case (2). Furthermore, whenever load sharing existed in case (1), the strength improvement was further increased. Some authors reported static strength improvements of up to 20% in hybrid joints with load sharing, compared to the bolted joint baseline [6]. Finally, whenever load sharing was achieved, the strength of the underlying bonded joint was found to improve *as well as* the strength of bolted joint [6,8,11]. This was not true in the absence of load sharing.

Author	Year	Model Type	Model Dimension	Contact	Clearance	Clamp-up	Adhesive Plasticity	Accuracy vs [5]	Computational Efficiency vs [10]
Paroissien [10]	2007	Analytical	2D	No	No	No	Yes	Fair	Excellent
Bois et al [11]	2013	Analytical	2D	No	No	No	Yes	Fair	Excellent
Barut et al [12]	2009	Numerical (Ritz)	3D	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Good	Good
Kelly [5]	2005	Numerical (FEM)	3D	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Excellent	Mediocre

Table 1: Overview of models for predicting load sharing in composite single-lap hybrid joints

Given the experimentally observed benefits of hybrid joints with load sharing, it is clearly desirable to be able to determine *a priori* whether a particular hybrid joint design will experience load sharing or not. A predictive model is thus required. A number of models of this kind currently exist in the literature, an overview of which is provided in Table 1 (in the current work, only single-lap, single-bolt joints are considered since this is the configuration of choice in a number of civil and military bolted joint standards [9]). As shown, the 2D analytical models [10-11] have limited prediction capabilities and generality due to the necessarily large number of simplifications. They thus require significant calibration based on more detailed 3D numerical models or experimental testing. In contrast, 3D elasticity based finite element models (3D-FEM) make few simplifications, but are computationally expensive [5]. The only other 3D hybrid joint analysis method in the literature, an equivalent single layer Rayleigh-Ritz numerical solution (ESL-RR), does not consider adhesive plasticity although it is relatively more efficient than 3D-FEM [12].

In order to adequately capture the physics of a real hybrid joint, it is necessary to take into account adhesive plasticity, bolt-to-laminate contact, bolt-hole clearance, bolt flexibility and bolt pre-tension. The aim of this paper is thus to develop and validate a new numerical model that accounts for all of these behaviours, yet simultaneously achieves a high level of computational efficiency, allowing for its use in sensitivity analysis and preliminary design studies of load sharing in hybrid joints.

2 MODEL OVERVIEW

In order to adequately account for the complex geometry, nonlinear adhesive behaviour and bolt-to-laminate contact in a hybrid joint, an approximate numerical solution technique must be used. The finite element method is well suited for this purpose. In the interest of time, the proposed model is solved using the commercial finite element software ABAQUS. Nevertheless, it must be kept in mind

that the model described in this paper is mathematical in nature and thus software independent. It could be solved using any number of other finite element software or dedicated code. The advantage of ABAQUS for the current application is ease of implementation and the possibility to write user subroutines, which shall be required to implement certain constraints on the Galerkin weak form, as shall be described.

2.1 MATHEMATICAL MODEL

The physical problem considered is depicted in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Single-bolt, single-lap joint geometry [1]

The proposed mathematical description of this problem shall consider the substrates to behave as Mindlin-Reissner plates, the bolt to behave as a Timoshenko Beam and the adhesive to behave as a 3D continuum solid. The kinematic, strain-displacement and constitutive equations for these structural entities are given in Table 2 below. Note that an infinitesimal strain assumption is implicit in the given strain-displacement equations. Also, the use of $\cdot j$ in subscripts denotes partial differentiation with respect to the variable j .

Mindlin-Reissner Plate	Timoshenko Beam	3D Continuum
Kinematic Equations		
$U_x^{(i)}(x, y, z) = u_x^{(i)}(x, y) - (z - z_i)\theta_x^{(i)}(x, y)$ $U_y^{(i)}(x, y, z) = u_y^{(i)}(x, y) - (z - z_i)\theta_y^{(i)}(x, y)$ $U_z^{(i)}(x, y, z) = u_z^{(i)}(x, y)$	$U_x^{(b)}(x, y, z) = u_x^{(b)}(z) - (x - x_0)\theta_x^{(b)}(z)$ $U_y^{(b)}(x, y, z) = u_y^{(b)}(z) - (y - y_0)\theta_y^{(b)}(z)$ $U_z^{(b)}(x, y, z) = u_z^{(b)}(z)$	$U_x^{(a)}(x, y, z)$ $U_y^{(a)}(x, y, z)$ $U_z^{(a)}(x, y, z)$
Strain-displacement Equations		
$\varepsilon_x^{(i)} = u_{x,x}^{(i)}, \quad \varepsilon_y^{(i)} = u_{y,y}^{(i)}, \quad \gamma_{xy}^{(i)} = \frac{1}{2}(u_{y,x}^{(i)} + u_{x,y}^{(i)})$ $\gamma_{xz}^{(i)} = u_{z,x}^{(i)} - \theta_x^{(i)}, \quad \gamma_{yz}^{(i)} = u_{z,y}^{(i)} - \theta_y^{(i)}$ $\kappa_x^{(i)} = -\theta_{x,x}^{(i)}$ $\kappa_y^{(i)} = -\theta_{y,y}^{(i)}$ $\kappa_{xy}^{(i)} = -\theta_{y,x}^{(i)} - \theta_{x,y}^{(i)}$	$\varepsilon_z^{(b)} = u_{z,z}^{(b)}$ $\gamma_{xz}^{(b)} = u_{z,x}^{(b)} - \theta_x^{(b)}, \quad \gamma_{yz}^{(b)} = u_{z,y}^{(b)} - \theta_y^{(b)}$ $\kappa_x^{(b)} = -\theta_{x,x}^{(b)}$ $\kappa_y^{(b)} = -\theta_{y,y}^{(b)}$	$\varepsilon_{ij}^{(a)} = \frac{1}{2}(u_{i,j}^{(a)} + u_{j,i}^{(a)})$
Constitutive Equations		
$\begin{bmatrix} N_x \\ N_y \\ N_{xy} \\ M_x \\ M_y \\ M_z \\ Q_{xz} \\ Q_{yz} \end{bmatrix}^{(i)} = \begin{bmatrix} A_{11} & A_{12} & A_{13} & B_{11} & B_{12} & B_{13} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ A_{12} & A_{22} & A_{23} & B_{12} & B_{22} & B_{23} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ A_{13} & A_{23} & A_{33} & B_{13} & B_{23} & B_{33} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ B_{11} & B_{12} & B_{13} & D_{11} & D_{12} & D_{13} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ B_{12} & B_{22} & B_{23} & D_{12} & D_{22} & D_{23} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ B_{13} & B_{23} & B_{33} & D_{13} & D_{23} & D_{33} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & G_{11} & G_{12} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & G_{12} & G_{22} & 0 \end{bmatrix}^{(i)} \begin{bmatrix} \varepsilon_x \\ \varepsilon_y \\ \gamma_{xy} \\ \kappa_x \\ \kappa_y \\ \kappa_{xy} \\ \gamma_{xz} \\ \gamma_{yz} \end{bmatrix}^{(i)}$	$\begin{bmatrix} N_z \\ M_x \\ M_y \\ Q_{xz} \\ Q_{yz} \end{bmatrix}^{(b)} = \begin{bmatrix} EA & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & EI & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & EI & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & kGA & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & kGA \end{bmatrix}^{(b)} \begin{bmatrix} \varepsilon_z \\ \kappa_x \\ \kappa_y \\ \gamma_{xz} \\ \gamma_{yz} \end{bmatrix}^{(b)}$	<div style="display: flex; align-items: center;"> <div style="margin-right: 20px;"> $\begin{bmatrix} \sigma_{xx} \\ \sigma_{yy} \\ \sigma_{zz} \\ \sigma_{xz} \\ \sigma_{yz} \end{bmatrix}^{(a)} = \begin{bmatrix} 2\mu + \lambda & \lambda & \lambda & 0 & 0 \\ \lambda & 2\mu + \lambda & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ \lambda & 0 & 2\mu + \lambda & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \mu & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \mu \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \varepsilon_{xx} \\ \varepsilon_{yy} \\ \varepsilon_{zz} \\ \gamma_{xz} \\ \gamma_{yz} \end{bmatrix}^{(a)}$ </div> <div> <p>Elastic region:</p> <p>Plastic region:</p> $\dot{\varepsilon}_a^p = \gamma \frac{\partial f}{\partial \sigma^{(a)}}$ </div> </div>

$$\begin{aligned}\dot{\alpha} &= -\gamma \mathbf{D} \frac{\partial f}{\partial \alpha} \\ f(\boldsymbol{\sigma}^{(a)}, \alpha) &= q - p \cdot \tan(\beta) - d \leq 0 \\ q &= \sqrt{\frac{3}{2}} \mathbf{S} : \mathbf{S} \\ d &= \left(1 + \frac{1}{3} \cdot \tan(\beta)\right) \cdot \sigma_{yt} \\ \gamma &\geq 0, \quad f(\boldsymbol{\sigma}^{(a)}, \alpha) \leq 0, \quad \gamma f(\boldsymbol{\sigma}^{(a)}, \alpha) = 0\end{aligned}$$

$u_j^{(i)}$ = jth displacement component of the ith plate midplane	$u_j^{(b)}$ = jth displacement component of the bolt neutral axis	$\boldsymbol{\sigma}^{(a)}$ = Adhesive Cauchy stress tensor
$\theta_j^{(i)}$ = jth rotation component of the ith plate midplane	$\theta_j^{(b)}$ = jth rotation component of the ith plate midplane	$\sigma_{ij}^{(a)}$ = ij component of the Cauchy stress tensor
$\varepsilon_j^{(i)}$ = jj normal strain component of the ith plate midplane	$\varepsilon_j^{(b)}$ = jj normal strain component of the bolt neutral axis	$\varepsilon_{ij}^{(a)}$ = ij component of the infinitesimal strain tensor
$\gamma_{jk}^{(i)}$ = jk shear strain component of the ith plate midplane	$\gamma_{ij}^{(b)}$ = ij shear strain component of the bolt neutral axis	\mathbf{S} = deviatoric part of the Cauchy stress tensor
$\kappa_j^{(i)}$ = jth curvature component of the ith plate midplane	$\kappa_j^{(b)}$ = jth curvature component of the bolt neutral axis	p = hydrostatic pressure
$N_j^{(i)}$ = jth stress resultant of the ith plate midplane	$E^{(b)}$ = Young's Modulus	β = material friction angle
$M_j^{(i)}$ = jth moment resultant of the ith plate midplane	$A^{(b)}$ = bolt cross-sectional area	q = von Mises stress
$Q_j^{(i)}$ = jth shear resultant of the ith plate midplane	$I^{(b)}$ = bolt second moment of area	μ = Lamé's first parameter
A_{ij} = ij component of the A matrix from CLPT	$k^{(b)}$ = transverse shear correction factor	λ = Lamé's second parameter
B_{ij} = ij component of the B matrix from CLPT	$N_z^{(b)}$ = bolt axial force	α = internal hardening variable
D_{ij} = ij component of the D matrix from CLPT	$M_j^{(b)}$ = jth moment resultant of the bolt neutral axis	\mathbf{D} = matrix of generalized plastic moduli
G_{ij} = ij component of the G matrix from Yang-Norris-Stavsky Theory	$\kappa_j^{(b)}$ = jth curvature component of the bolt neutral axis	γ = consistency parameter
		f = yield surface
		σ_{yt} = tensile yield stress

Table 2: Kinematic, strain-displacement and constitutive equations of proposed model

The constitutive equations for the plates and beam are linear anisotropic (classical laminated plate theory i.e. CLPT with first order shear deformation) and linear isotropic (first order shear deformation beam theory), respectively. For the adhesive, a nonlinear constitutive equation is used as it has been determined by several authors that adhesive nonlinearity has a significant effect on load sharing. A general yet simple elastic-plastic model is used, namely the Drucker-Prager yield criterion with associated flow and isotropic hardening. This model allows for dependency of yield on both the hydrostatic and deviatoric components of the Cauchy stress tensor. Finally, the governing equations are conservation of linear momentum and conservation of angular momentum:

$$\rho \dot{\mathbf{v}} + \nabla \cdot \boldsymbol{\sigma} - \rho \mathbf{b} = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma} = \boldsymbol{\sigma}^T \quad (2)$$

where ρ is density, \mathbf{b} are the body forces and $\boldsymbol{\sigma}$ is the Cauchy stress tensor. The acceleration term in (1) is set to zero as only the quasi-static problem is considered.

2.1.1 CONTACT

Beams are considered to be transversely inextensible and therefore in the current model, it is assumed that there is unilateral contact between the deformable laminate hole and the rigid bolt shank surface in the laminate midplane. Furthermore, the bolt head is also considered to be rigid and in unilateral contact with the laminate surface. In both cases, non-penetrability is assumed to exist in the normal direction while a Coulomb friction law governs the contact tangential behavior. This is described by the following equations:

Normal Direction	Tangential Direction
$g_N \geq 0$	$g_T^e = g_T - g_T^s$
$P_N \geq 0$	$t_T = c_T g_T^e$
$g_N P_N = 0$	$\dot{g}_T^s = \dot{\gamma} \frac{t_T}{\ t_T\ }$
	$\dot{\gamma} \geq 0, f_s(t_T) \leq 0, \dot{\gamma} f_s(t_T) = 0$
g_N = normal gap	g_T^e = elastic tangential slip
P_N = normal pressure	g_T^s = plastic tangential slip
	g_T = total tangential slip
	t_T = tangential traction vector
	$\dot{\gamma}$ = consistency parameter

Table 3: Contact equations of proposed model

2.1.2 KINEMATIC CONSTRAINTS

The contact between the bolt shank and substrate hole bearing surface is considered at the laminate midplane – such a simplification is inevitable since an equivalent single layer (ESL) plate theory is used. The choice of the midplane as the plane in which the hole contact analysis is performed is critical to accurately capture the physics of the bolt bending. Other authors have made the same assumption previously [13]. However, since the adhesive does not physically attach to the laminate midplane, but rather to its surface, the displacements of the adhesive and laminate along their interface must therefore be constrained as follows:

$$U_\alpha^{(ta)}(x, y, z) = U_\alpha^{0(tl)}(x, y) + \psi_\alpha^{(tl)}(x, y) \cdot \frac{t^{(tl)}}{2} | \alpha = x, y \quad (3)$$

$$U_z^{(ta)}(x, y, z) = U_z^{0(tl)}(x, y) \quad (4)$$

$$U_\alpha^{(ba)}(x, y, z) = U_\alpha^{0(bl)}(x, y) - \psi_\alpha^{(bl)}(x, y) \cdot \frac{t^{(bl)}}{2} | \alpha = x, y \quad (5)$$

$$U_z^{(bl)}(x, y, z) = U_z^{0(bl)}(x, y) \quad (6)$$

Here U_α, U_z are the adhesive surface displacement components, U_α^0, U_z^0 are the laminate midplane displacement components, ψ_α are the laminate midplane rotation components and t is the laminate thickness. The superscript in brackets defines the adhesive surface or laminate in question – ta, ba referring to the top and bottom adhesive surfaces respectively while tl, bl refer to the top and bottom laminates.

2.2 FINITE ELEMENT SOLUTION

Based on the above strain-displacement and constitutive equations, the weak form of the governing equations can be obtained using the principle of virtual work. The weak form must subsequently be constrained to enforce the aforementioned kinematic constraints. This is achieved using Lagrange multipliers. A discrete approximation of the solution is hence substituted into the weak form. For the proposed model, a finite element approximation is used. Note that the formation of the discrete equations and integration of the terms in the weak form is handled internally by ABAQUS. The nonlinear elastic behaviour and contact are also handled internally by ABAQUS using appropriate time-stepping techniques and associated algorithms, e.g., return mapping.

2.2.1 DISCRETIZATION AND ELEMENT CHOICE

The substrates, bolt and adhesive are modeled in ABAQUS as Mindlin-Reissner plates, Timoshenko beams and continuum solids respectively. The relevant ABAQUS elements are the S8R, B32 and C3D20R elements. Quadratic element interpolating functions are used to provide a fast solution convergence rate and to enable good adhesive element aspect ratios for thin bondlines. To simplify the analysis, the grip regions are not considered (this is justified by invoking Saint Venant's principle). A typical model discretization is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Finite element mesh and boundary conditions [14]

To limit the discrete number of degrees-of-freedom in the model, a single layer of solid elements is meshed through the adhesive thickness. An extensive mesh convergence study was performed and showed that this provides good convergence for the bolt shear load between successive mesh refinements (to within 0.5%), for bondline thicknesses ranging from 0.1 to 1mm. Other authors have independently found the single layer quadratic solid approach to provide excellent stress and strain results when compared with analytical bonded joint solutions.

The beam elements must be augmented with a number of rigid surfaces for the definition of contact with the substrates. Analytical rigid surfaces are used for this purpose in ABAQUS. Two rigid cylinders are connected to the bolt shank using a *TIE constraint (one at each laminate midplane). To simulate the boltheads, rigid discs are used. This augmented bolt model is shown in Figure 3. Small sliding contact is defined in ABAQUS between the laminate surface and discs, and the laminate hole edge and cylinders. In accordance with the mathematical model, Coulomb friction must be specified in the contact settings.

Figure 3: Bolt model [14]

2.2.2 SECTIONS

The constitutive equations are implemented in the ABAQUS finite element model by assigning appropriate section properties to the various elements. Each section requires specification of the material and section thickness, layup, etc.

2.2.3 MULTIPOINT CONSTRAINTS

The multipoint constraints (MPC) defined by Eqns. (4) and (6) can be easily implemented in ABAQUS using a coupling constraint in the z-direction between the adhesive nodes and matching substrate nodes in the overlap region. However, ABAQUS does not have a built-in MPC of the type given by Eqns. (3) and (5). It is nevertheless possible to enforce these constraints using a user-defined subroutine of type *MPC. A FORTRAN code must be written for this purpose. As previously described, the point of these constraints is to eliminate the need for the shell and solid nodes to be coincident. This allows the laminate *midplane* to be used in the contact detection and force transmission into the beam, which is essential for correctly modeling the bolt bending. The use of the developed *MPC subroutine in a bonded joint is demonstrated in Figure 4. Note that in the coincident node model, the section properties must be offset, whereas in the *MPC model this is not necessary since the shells are located at the laminate midplane (as was desired).

Figure 4: User defined MPCs

2.2.4 BOUNDARY CONDITIONS

The model described so far does not have a unique solution since the system is not sufficiently constrained, i.e., the boundary conditions are not specified. In order to obtain a unique solution, the boundary conditions shown in Figure 2 are applied to the model. On the LHS, the DOFs are directly set to zero. On the RHS, a *TIE constraint is used to constrain the joint edge DOFs to the motion of a control point, to which the specified boundary conditions and desired displacement/force loads are applied.

3 EXPERIMENTAL VALIDATION

The accuracy of the described mathematical model for predicting load sharing and deformation of a hybrid joint was verified experimentally. This necessitated the selection of suitable design parameters that would induce significant bolt load transfer (based on the model predictions). Specialized tooling was used to manufacture the corresponding hybrid joint. Next, an instrumented bolt was designed, manufactured and calibrated in order to allow the bolt shear load to be measured. Finally, the bolt was installed in the joint and a uniaxial tension test was performed in a tensile testing machine, during which bolt shear and machine displacement were recorded.

3.1 SPECIMEN GEOMETRY AND MANUFACTURE

The bolted joint geometry specified in the ASTM D5961 standard [9] was adapted in order to ensure that the hybrid achieved significant load sharing. Final joint dimensions are given in Table 4.

L_a (mm)	L_f (mm)	L_g (mm)	D (mm)	W (mm)	t_a (mm)	t (mm)	D_h (mm)
32.0	85.0	30.0	8.002	28.0	0.51	4.39	11.9

Table 4: Validation joint dimensions [14]

E_{11} (GPa)	$E_{22} = E_{33}$ (GPa)	$G_{12} = G_{13}$ (GPa)	G_{23} (GPa)	ν_{12}	ν_{13}	ν_{23}
141	9.70	5.10	3.40	0.33	0.33	0.44

Table 5: Cytec 5320 CFRP tape properties [14]

The substrates and doublers were manufactured from Cytec 5320 CFRP prepreg tape (for properties see Table 5). First, a plate was laid up with a stacking sequence of $[45/0/-45/90]_4s$. Since 5320 is an out-of-autoclave material, the plate was cured in an oven under vacuum as per manufacturer specifications. The substrates and doublers were cut from the plate using a diamond saw, before being assembled and bonded inside a custom-built mold (see Figure 5). This mold was designed to achieve precise control of the substrate alignment. Mold spacers were used to control the bondline thickness, spew fillet geometry and joint overlap length.

Figure 5: Bonded Joint Mold Containing a Single Joint

In order to help induce significant load sharing, a weak yet ductile epoxy adhesive was chosen to bond the components (Hysol EA-9361). A Thinky ARE-310 centrifugal mixer was used to mix the different adhesive parts and ensure uniform and consistent mixing. The joint was left to cure at room temperature for a period of 1 week, as per manufacturer recommendations. Upon demolding, a hole was drilled at the center of the joint overlap using a CNC drill. A Sandvik-Coromant Corodril 854 drillbit was used for this purpose, which is specifically designed for tight-tolerance drilling of composites. Subsequent inspection found the hole diameter to be $8 \text{ mm } +25.4/-0 \text{ } \mu\text{m}$.

3.2 INSTRUMENTED BOLT DESIGN AND CALIBRATION

For the instrumented bolt, a stud design was adopted as shown in Figure 6. To manufacture the bolt, first the bolt shank was cut from a tight-tolerance, precision ground rod of easy-to-machine 416 stainless steel ($E = 205 \text{ GPa}$, $\nu = 0.3$). This rod had a diametric tolerance of $8 \text{ mm } +0/-4 \text{ } \mu\text{m}$ (a diameter of 7.999 mm was measured using a micrometer). The screw threads were hence turned on a lathe after which diametrically opposing strain gauge slots were cut into the bolt shank using a CNC milling machine. Within each slot, a pair of shear strain gauges was bonded to the bolt surface. Figure 6 shows the first pair of strain gauges (SG1 / SG2) on one side of the bolt; the other pair (SG3 / SG4) was located in the opposing slot. Small lead wires (38 AGW) were soldered to the gauges (see Figure 7) and routed out of the joint through the wiring channels shown and slots cut into the top washer. Away from the joint, the wires were soldered to a printed circuit board (PCB) on which they were connected in a full Wheatstone bridge. Finally, the PCB was connected to the data acquisition system (DAQ) using a shielded cable.

Figure 6: Instrumented bolt assembly section view from side (dimensions in mm) [14]

Figure 7: Instrumented bolt during strain gauge coating cure

The reasoning behind the adopted stud design was to allow the bolt's shear plane to be adjusted within the joint and to be aligned with the adhesive midplane. Furthermore, a hex slot machined into the bolt end allowed the bolt to be accurately positioned radially. However, bolt installation was not perfectly repeatable. To account for this installation error, as well as to determine the relationship between the measurement circuit output (in mV/V) and applied bolt shear load (in N), five separate calibration tests were performed with the instrumented bolt installed in a bolted joint. This calibration joint was identical to the hybrid joint specimen used in the validation except for the absence of adhesive. Nevertheless, a thin silicon sheet was used to simulate the additional substrate offset due to the bondline. No torque was applied to the nuts such that the silicon itself did not transfer any significant load through friction. The calibration setup is shown in Figure 8. For each calibration test, a linear regression was fitted to the potential difference measured by the Wheatstone bridge versus the known bolt shear load i.e. the total applied machine load. A mean regression was hence calculated; the maximum error predicted between any calibration test and the mean regression was 8%. This provides a good degree of confidence that the measurement precision of the instrumented bolt, taking into account the installation error, was within 10% inside the 0-5 kN calibration range.

Figure 8: Instrumented bolt installed in the bolted calibration joint

After each calibration test, the bolt shear load measurement was always found to return to zero. This confirms that the tests were within the elastic regime of the bolt and that no damage had occurred that could have interfered with the calibration.

3.3 ADHESIVE CHARACTERIZATION

The adhesive tensile stress-strain curve was obtained following the ASTM D638 standard. The measured curve is shown in Figure 9. A 5 kN electromechanical tensile testing machine was used to load an adhesive dogbone specimen at a rate of 0.006 mm/s, while digital image correlation (DIC) was used to record the strains in the specimen. Due to time and cost constraints, the pressure sensitivity of yield of the adhesive was not characterized. In the validation model, pressure insensitivity of yield is therefore assumed, i.e., $\beta = 0$.

Figure 9: EA-9361 stress-strain curve [14]

3.4 VALIDATION EXPERIMENT

The validation hybrid joint was installed in a 100 kN hydraulic tensile testing machine. The bolt was installed in the joint in the same way as in the calibration tests, and the joint was loaded in displacement control at a rate of 0.006 mm/s to 10 kN. As in the calibration tests, the bolt shear load, machine load and machine displacement were recorded. An analysis was hence performed using the proposed model and the validation parameters given in Tables 1-2, which was then compared with the experimental data. The load-displacement predicted by the proposed model versus the measured

experimental data is compared in Figure 10. Good agreement is observed between the model and the experimental measurements. The maximum absolute error in displacement is 0.04 mm, occurring at a total applied load of 10 kN, which represents relative error of a 7%.

Figure 10: Load-displacement validation

The load sharing (bolt load/total load) predicted by the proposed model is compared with the experimental results in Figure 11. As can be seen, the experimental measurements and proposed model agree very closely for most of the tested displacement range, up to a displacement of 0.5 mm. Beyond this, the agreement is less good, although still acceptable. One reason for the breakdown in model accuracy at higher loads/displacements is that the small strain assumption breaks down. Furthermore, more complex adhesive behavior that is not accounted for in the model such as creep and hyperelasticity may also have some effect. However, as a whole, the experimental measurements and model agree very well. The largest absolute error between the measured bolt shear load and model prediction was 300 N, occurring at a total applied load of 10 kN. This represents a relative error of 8.5%, which is within the measurement accuracy range established during the instrumented bolt calibration. A maximum load sharing condition of 35% was measured at this same load level, confirming that significant load sharing was achieved during the experiment.

Figure 11: Load sharing validation

On the basis of these comparisons with measured validation data, it can be concluded that the proposed numerical model is able to provide a good prediction of load-sharing in a real hybrid joint. Furthermore, a separate comprehensive study has found the present model's prediction to be equally good as those provided by a detailed 3D-FEM, which justifies the simplifying assumptions made. In addition, in this same study, it was shown that the proposed model was able to achieve computational efficiency savings of over 95% compared to the detailed 3D-FEM, with a runtime for the validation joint model of 242 seconds versus 5436 seconds for the 3D-FEM [1].

5 CONCLUSIONS

To date, there has been no model for predicting load sharing in a single lap, single bolt composite bonded-bolted joint that is both comprehensive and computationally efficient. Such a model is developed and validated in the current work. The model is shown to predict load sharing with good accuracy compared to measurements made during a specially devised validation experiment. Importantly, the proposed model provides >95% computational savings compared to an equivalent 3D-FEM, due to the use of efficient equivalent single layer/equivalent single axis structural entities to represent the substrates and bolt. This good efficiency means that the model has the potential to be used in preliminary design studies and sensitivity analyses.

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